

Population genomics supports clonal reproduction and multiple gains and losses of parasitic abilities in the most devastating nematode plant pest

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Species	Tobacco	Tomato	Watermelon	Peanut	Pepper	Cotton
	NC 95	Rutgers	Charleston Gray	Florunner	Early California Wonder	Deltapine 61
<i>M. incognita</i>						
Race 1	-	+	+	-	+	-
Race 2	+	+	+	-	+	-
Race 3	-	+	+	-	+	+
Race 4	+	+	+	-	+	+
<i>M. arenaria</i>						
Race 1	+	+	+	+	+	-
Race 2	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>M. javanica</i>						
	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>M. hapla</i>						
	+	+	-	+	+	-

Table S1. Expected host reactions of the NCDHT to discriminate *M. incognita* races.

Nematode reproduction indexes (average of 4 replicates) were used to determine cotton and tobacco as good/susceptible (+) or poor/resistant (-) hosts. Tobacco and cotton are highlighted (light grey shadow) to show that the differentiation of the four *M. incognita* races is determined by the combined reaction of these two hosts alone.

Isolate	Raw		After Trimming			
	PE reads #	No. of bases	PE reads #	No. of bases	Coverage	Mapped (%)
R1-2	77.0E+06	23.1E+09	76.4E+06	22.7E+09	122.53	97.39
R1-3	76.2E+06	22.9E+09	75.5E+06	22.4E+09	121.20	99.51
R1-6	75.8E+06	22.8E+09	75.0E+06	22.3E+09	120.55	97.28
R2-1	75.7E+06	22.7E+09	75.1E+06	22.3E+09	120.41	98.96
R2-6	76.0E+06	22.8E+09	75.3E+06	22.4E+09	121.01	94.26
R3-1	75.1E+06	22.5E+09	74.5E+06	22.1E+09	119.51	89.34
R3-2	75.3E+06	22.6E+09	74.7E+06	22.2E+09	119.92	98.16
R3-4	75.3E+06	22.6E+09	74.6E+06	22.2E+09	119.79	98.47
R4-1	75.6E+06	22.7E+09	75.1E+06	22.3E+09	120.52	99.04
R4-3	75.8E+06	22.8E+09	75.2E+06	22.4E+09	120.89	97.00
R4-4	75.6E+06	22.7E+09	75.0E+06	22.3E+09	120.46	99.32

Table S2. Statistics of generated sequence data and genome coverage per isolate.

Number of Illumina paired-end reads and amount of bases generated per isolate. Values indicated before and after quality filtering (trimming). Coverage values of mapped reads are given according to a reference genome size of 184 Mb.

Fig. S1. Distribution of base coverage per category of SNP on the reference genome for each isolate.

Density plot of base coverage for homozygous identical (0/0) heterozygous SNP (0/1) and homozygous SNP.

Fig. S2. Distribution of average per base coverage in 100bp windows on the *M. incognita* reference genome.

Illumina reads used to produce the reference *M. incognita* genome assembly¹ were mapped back to the reference genome using the same methodology as for the 11 isolates. Average per base coverage for each 100bp window was counted and the density at each coverage was plotted.

Text S1. Test for association between SNP-based clusters and biological traits

We tested for significant association between the SNP-based clusters of the different *M. incognita* isolates and the following biological traits:

- Pattern of host compatibility (= host races)
- Nature of the crop plant of origin at the moment of isolation
- Geographical distribution

For the two first above-mentioned biological traits we used a Fisher's exact test while for geographical distance, we used Isolation By Distance (IBD) analysis. All these analyses were performed based on the data gathered in the Table S4 (below).

Name	Cluster	Race	Host	Country	Region	City	GPS coordinates
R1-2	A	1	Soybean	Brazil	PR	Londrina	23°18'22.0"S 51°10'07.9"W
R3-2	B	3	Soybean	Brazil	PR	Londrina	23°18'22.0"S 51°10'07.9"W
R4-4	B	4	Cotton	Brazil	SP	Vargem Grande do Sul	21°49'52.9"S 46°53'24.3"W
R2-1	C	2	Tobacco	Brazil	SC	Sombrio	29°05'54.0"S 49°37'50.5"W
R2-6	C	2	Coffee	Brazil	PR	São Jorge do Patrocínio	23°43'47.2"S 53°56'38.4"W
R1-3	C	1	Cucumber	Brazil	SP	Piracicaba	22°44'05.1"S 47°38'48.2"W
R1-6	C	1	Tobacco	Brazil	PR	Mercedes	24°27'13.1"S 54°10'04.5"W
R4-3	C	4	Watermelon	Brazil	PR	Londrina	23°18'22.0"S 51°10'07.9"W
R3-1	C	3	Cotton	Brazil	PR	Umuarama	23°46'22.0"S 53°18'34.4"W
R4-1	C	4	Cotton	Brazil	MT	Campo Verde	15°33'32.0"S 55°10'04.3"W
R3-4	C	3	Cotton	Brazil	PR, MS, BA	Umuarama, Londrina, Dourados, L.E. Magalhães	NA: pool of species
A14	A	NA	Tomato	Libya	North East	NA	32°43'51.6"N 22°07'47.4"E
L9	A	NA	NA	Ivory Coast	NA	NA	7°42'42.4"N 5°02'17.4"W
L19	A	NA	NA	French West Indies	Guadeloupe	NA	16°12'26.0"N 61°40'13.1"W
Morelos	C	3	NA	Mexico	Morelos	Morelos	18°45'11.1"N 99°06'29.7"W
L27	C	1	NA	USA	NA	NA	NA: US state not known
W1	C	NA	Tomato	USA	California	Yolo County	38°44'22.1"N 121°48'35.4"W
557R	C	NA	Tomato	USA	North Carolina	NA	35°49'30.3"N 78°39'11.9"W
HarC	C	NA	Grape	USA	California	NA	34°13'03.2"N 117°32'54.8"W
VW6	C	NA	Cotton	USA	California	NA	34°13'03.2"N 117°32'54.8"W

Table S3. Cluster assignment, host race status, host of origin and geographical origin of the 11 isolates.

Association between genetic clusters and host races

The Fisher's exact test checks for independency between the tested variables, based on the co-occurrence counts.

We used the following contingency table of the 13 isolates (including the L27 isolate characterized as Race 1 and the Morelos isolate characterized as a Race 3) in clusters and host races:

Cluster / Host Race	R1	R2	R3	R4
A	1	0	0	0
B	0	0	1	1
C	3	2	3	2

The Fisher exact test returns a p-value of 1 indicating no significant association between host races and SNP clusters of isolates.

To evaluate the sensitivity of the Fisher's exact test, we also ran the same test on an artificially modified contingency table. In this modified contingency table, we assigned all the R3 to cluster B and all the R4 to cluster C and left the rest of the table unchanged.

Cluster / Host Race	R1	R2	R3	R4
A	1	0	0	0
B	0	0	4	0
C	3	2	0	3

This modification alone was enough to obtain a p-value of 0.007, indicating that this method is sensitive in detecting significant association between genetic clusters and biological traits.

Association between genetic clusters and the nature of the crop of origin

For crop species, we performed two analyses.

- 1. All the isolates for which a crop species of origin was documented regardless the number of occurrences of the crop species (16 isolates on 8 different crops cf. Table S4).

Cluster	Coffee	Cotton	Cucumber	Grape	Soybean	Tobacco	Tomato	Watermel
A	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
B	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
C	1	4	1	1	0	2	2	1

The Fisher exact test returns a p-value of 0.69, indicating no significant association between crop species and clusters

- 2. All the isolate / crop species associations where host species count was >1 to eliminate potential biases associated to single isolate crop species (12 isolates on 4 different crops c.f. Table S4)

Cluster	Cotton	Soybean	Tobacco	Tomato
A	0	1	0	1
B	1	1	0	0
C	4	0	2	2

The Fisher exact test returns a p-value of 0.26, indicating, here again, no significant association between crop species and clusters.

Fig. S3. Isolation by Distance (IBD) analysis between the 11 Brazilian isolates.

Each pair of isolates is plotted in a scatterplot where the x-axis is the geographical distance and the y-axis is the genetic distance. Density of points is represented by different colours (blue - low, red - high).

	Cluster A	Cluster B	Cluster C
Cluster A	X	0.98088	0.3523
Cluster B	0.9904	X	0.52805
Cluster C	0.83675	0.84255	X

Table S4. Fixation index (F_{ST}) based on homozygous SNPs (upper part mean values, lower part weighted values).

Fig. S5. Phylogenetic analysis based on SNPS present in the 14 biggest scaffolds with enough variable positions in coding regions

Unrooted topologies of all the ML trees constructed from SNPs present in coding regions for the 14 longest scaffolds containing such SNPs in enough abundance.

Fig. S6. Phylogenetic analysis based on SNPs in the mitochondrial genome

The tree topology exactly recapitulates the one obtained at the nuclear level.

Fig. S7. Isolation by Distance (IBD) analysis between all the *M. incognita* isolates available worldwide.

Each pair of isolates is plotted in a scatterplot where the x-axis is the geographical distance and the y-axis is the genetic distance. Density of points is represented by different colours (blue - low, red - high).

Fig. S8. Reconstruction of the ancestral states using PastML with the ML MPAA method. *M. incognita* host races (R1-R4) are defined by differential compatibilities on Tobacco and Cotton. The left semicircle displays the probability of node being able to parasitise tobacco while the right semicircle displays the probability of the node being able to parasitise cotton.

Species	Primer	Sequence (5'→3')	Length (bp)	Reference
<i>M. exigua</i>	ex-D15F	CATCCGTGCTGTAGCTGCGAG	562	Randig et al., 2002
	ex-D15R	CTCCGTGGGAAGAAAGACTG		
<i>M. incognita</i>	inc-K15F	GGGATGTGTAAATGCTCCTG	399	Randig et al., 2002
	inc-K15R	CCCGCTACACCCTCAACTTC		
<i>M. paranaensis</i>	par-C09F	GCCCGACTCCATTTGACGGA	208	Randig et al., 2002
	par-C09R	CCGTCCAGATCCATCGAAGTC		
<i>M. javanica</i>	Fjav	GGTGCGCGATTGAACTGAGC	670	Zijlstra et al., 2000
	Rjav	CAGGCCCTTCAGTGGA ACTATAC		

Table S5. List of the SCAR molecular markers used for *Meloidogyne* spp. confirmation